

Standard Operating Procedure	Version: 2
Laboratory Processing of Environmental samples	
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Version History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	01/04/19	Initial version
2.0	01/07/19	Changes after initial pilot phase

1. Introduction

This method is applicable to the processing of environmental samples from households included in the DRUM study.

The proportion of patients admitted to hospitals in Uganda and Malawi with invasive infections caused by ESBL resistant Enterobacteriaceae including ESBL E coli (ESBL-E) and ESBL K pneumoniae (ESBL-K) is increasing. Given the reduced availability of Carbapenems, many of these drug-resistant infections are locally untreatable. To understand the drivers of this antimicrobial resistance, further evidence of the role of household environment contamination on human and animal carriage with ESBL-E and ESBL-K is required.

2. Purpose

These methods will be used to process environmental samples received into the laboratory from the DRUM study.

3. Responsibilities

- Field workers
 - Collection of human and animal stool, and environmental samples in according to Sample Collection SOPs
 - Correct labelling of collection samples
 - Prompt transport of collected samples to the laboratory
 - Completion of sample collection log
 - Inform Study Laboratory Technicians of sample arrival
- Study Laboratory Technicians
 - Receive samples from field and complete sample collection log
 - Register samples on DRUM eLIMS / teleform system
 - Ensure prompt collection of study samples from laboratory reception
 - Double-check correct sample labelling
 - Processing of environmental samples in accordance with this SOP

- Storage of samples for further analysis in accordance with this SOP
- Principal Investigators
 - Ensure laboratory training in sample processing procedures provided
 - Undertake quality control checks of laboratory processing.

4. Procedure

4.1 Storage conditions

All reagents should be stored as per the instructions of the manufacturer

4.2. Processing Sponge-stick Environmental Samples

4.2.1. Materials Needed Sponge-stick Environmental Samples

Sterile Buffered Peptone Water (at room temperature)

Falcon tube, measuring cylinder (or 25ml pipette + pipetboy)

1.8ml Cryovials

Pipette & 1000ul pipette tips

4.2.2 Test Procedure – Processing Sponge-stick Environmental Samples

1. Environmental swabs should arrive in sealed bag with 10ml of BPW present inside.
2. Open the bag and pour in a further 20ml of BPW (at room temperature), so a total volume of ~30ml is used.
3. Reseal the bag (including the sponge inside), ensure it is correctly labelled and incubate the in aerobic incubator at 37°C for 18-24 hours.
4. Document on the DRUM eLIMS / teleform, system
5. At the end of 18-24 hours incubation, take a 1.8ml aliquot of the culture media and place it in a cryovial for storage at -80°C. Generate freezer-safe LIMS barcode and apply to the tube and write the LIMS number on the tube also.

Record position on box plan on DRUM shared drive (recording patient ID) and store at -80°C.

6. Keep the remaining culture in the fridge if not proceeding to culture within <2hrs, for future processing.
7. Otherwise, proceed to ESBL culture (SOP4).

4.3.1. Materials Needed 3M Environmental Swab Samples

1.8ml Cryovials

Pipette & 1000ul pipette tips

4.3.2 Test Procedure – Processing of 3M Environmental Swab Samples

1. Environmental swabs should arrive in sealed tube with 10ml of BPW present inside.
2. Briefly vortex the sample
3. Incubate the sample at 37°C for 18-24 hours, with the lid is untightened slightly.
4. Ensure it is correctly labelled and incubate the in aerobic incubator at 37°C for 18-24 hours.
5. Document on the DRUM eLIMS / teleform system
6. At the end of 18-24 hours incubation, take a 1.8ml aliquot of the culture media and place it in a cryovial for storage at -80°C. Generate freezer-safe LIMS barcode and apply to the tube and write the LIMS number on the tube also. Record position on box plan on DRUM shared drive (recording patient ID) and store at -80°C.
7. Keep the remaining culture in the fridge if not proceeding to culture within <2hrs, for future processing.
8. Otherwise, proceed to ESBL culture (SOP4).

4.4.1 Water Sample Processing

4.4.2 Materials needed – Water Sample Processing

Water filter paper (0.45um)

Sterile tweezers

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Sterile scissors
Filter cups and manifolds
Baby steriliser
Sterile 30ml Containers (or autoclavable 30ml glass vials)
Sterile Buffered Peptone Water (at room temperature)
Falcon tube or measuring cylinder
1.8ml Cryovials
Pipette & 1000ul pipette tips
Autoclaved squares of aluminium foil
Autoclave tape
Sample bag

4.4.3 Test Procedure – Water Sample Processing

1. Water samples should arrive in a sealed Nalgene bottle.
2. Filter a measured volume of the water sample through a sterile 0.45µm cellulose ester gridded membrane on the vacuumed filter.
 - a. **For River water:** filter 500mL through 2 membranes (250mL in each)
 - i. Aseptically add the **first** membrane to the manifold.
 1. Homogenise the river water by inverting it 3-4 times
 2. Filter 250mL river water through this membrane and place it into a sterile container with 30ml of BPW (pre-incubated at room temperature), using sterile tweezers.
 3. Ensure it is correctly labelled and incubate the container in aerobic incubator at 37°C for 18-24 hours.
 4. Document this on the DRUM eLIMS / teleform system
 - ii. Aseptically add the **second** membrane to the manifold
 1. Then filter the final 250mL through a new sterile membrane and using sterile tweezers place this membrane onto autoclaved foil.
 2. Fold the foil over the membrane, ensuring no gaps are present, creating a parcel, and stick the parcel down with tape.

3. Mark on the tape the Sample ID using a permanent marker, and then place the foil parcel into a sample bag.
 4. Place the bag into the water filter box in the -80°C freezer.
 5. Document this on the DRUM eLIMS / teleform system
- b. **For all other water types (stored/source/rinse):** filter 500mL through
1 membrane
1. Place it into a sterile container with 30ml of BPW (pre-incubated at room temperature), using sterile tweezers.
 2. Ensure it is correctly labelled and incubate the container in aerobic incubator at 37°C for 18-24 hours.
 3. Document this on the DRUM eLIMS / teleform system
3. OPTIONAL: Given time restraints, it is possible to filter less than the total 500mL volume of water (for logistical purposes).
- a. Please review how much water has filtered through the membrane in 1.5hrs, and then at this point filter until the either 500mL, 250mL, 100mL or 50mL has been reached (whichever is closest in volume).
 - b. Mark the volume that was filtered on the telepath form
 - i. If the laboratory processing is progressing well, then it is optimal to filter until 500mL has been reached. So filtering times of greater than 1.5hrs are allowed to reach the final volume of 500mL, if laboratory processing allows.
4. At the end of 18-24 hours incubation, take a 1.8ml aliquot of the culture media and place it in a cryovial for storage at -80°C. Generate freezer-safe LIMS barcode and apply to the tube and write the LIMS number on the tube also. Record position on box plan on DRUM shared drive (recording patient ID) and store at -80°C.
 5. Keep the remaining culture in the fridge if not proceeding to culture within <2hrs, for future processing.
 6. Otherwise, proceed to ESBL culture (SOP4).

4.5 Test Procedure – Food Sample Processing

- Decide how to process food samples dependant on the type of food that is received into the laboratory.
 - a. Green leafy vegetables and Fruit will be processed in a different fashion, as below:

4.5.1. Green Leafy vegetables.

1. Green leafy vegetables should arrive in sealed Whirl-pac bag, and should be clearly labelled.
2. Weight the bag (and minus the weight of an empty Whirl-pac bag). This will give you the weight of the vegetables inside.
3. Aseptically, add nine times that weight (or volume) of BPW, pre-warmed to room temperature). It is important to maintain the sample: diluent volume at 1:9 (1 in 10). Avoid touching the inside of the bag with the hands at all times.
4. Homogenise for between 30 seconds and 3 minutes in a stomacher (or by hand).
 - a. The homogenisation time required will depend on the manufacturer instructions and the type of sample being examined.
 - b. If a stomacher is not operational, please manually homogenise the sample with your hands for 30 seconds.
 - c. Document on the DRUM eLIMS / teleform system
5. Ensure the bag is correctly labelled and place in an upright position, in a box/rack.
6. Incubate in an aerobic incubator at 37°C for 18-24 hours.
7. Document on the DRUM eLIMS / teleform system
8. At the end of 18-24 hours incubation, take a 1.8ml aliquot of the culture media and place it in a cryovial for storage at -80°C. Generate freezer-safe LIMS barcode and apply to the tube and write the LIMS number on the tube also. Record position on box plan on DRUM shared drive and store at -80°C.
9. Keep the remaining culture in the fridge if not proceeding to culture within <2hrs, for future processing.
10. Otherwise, proceed to ESBL culture (SOP4).

4.5.1. Fruit.

1. Fruit should arrive in sealed Whirl-pac bag and be clearly labelled.
2. Aseptically, add enough BPW (pre-warmed to room temperature) to cover the fruit. Start with 30mls and add more if required. Avoid touching the inside of the bag with the hands at all times.
3. Seal the bag and rub the BPW on the outside of the fruit for 30sec to 3min, being careful to get into any cracks around the stem.
4. Leave the bag to stand on the benchtop for roughly 10mins.
5. Then after 10mins, aseptically remove the fruit from the bag, and dispose of the fruit into the waste. This should leave the BPW in the bottom of the bag.
6. Ensure the bag is correctly labelled, re-seal and place in an upright position, in a box/rack.
7. Incubate in an aerobic incubator at 37°C for 18-24 hours.
8. Document on the DRUM eLIMS / teleform system
9. At the end of 18-24 hours incubation, take a 1.8ml aliquot of the culture media and place it in a cryovial for storage at -80°C. Generate freezer-safe LIMS barcode and apply to the tube and write the LIMS number on the tube also. Record position on box plan on DRUM shared drive (recording patient ID) and store at -80°C.
10. Keep the remaining culture in the fridge if not proceeding to culture within <2hrs, for future processing.
11. Otherwise, proceed to ESBL culture (SOP4).

4.6 Test Procedure – Clothing Sample Processing

- *Please follow procedure as described in 4.3 above, as a 3M sponge-stick will be used to collect clothing samples.*

4.7 Test Procedure – Soil / Floor Sample Processing

- *If floor/soil sample has been collected with a 3M sponge-stick, then process as above in 4.3.*

- *If floor/soil sample has been collected with boot-socks, please follow the processing below.*

1. Boot socks should arrive in a sealed Whirl-pac bag from the field.
2. Using aseptic technique, open the bag and pour in enough BPW to cover the boot sock. This may be more than 30ml. Avoid touching the inside of the bag with the hands.
3. Once the boot sock has been covered, reseal the bag, using the wire closure.
4. Homogenise the bag, with your hands to ensure that all of the boot socks have been covered in BPW and the soil/debris is loose in the BPW.
5. Ensure the bag is correctly labelled and the bag in an upright position, in a box/rack.
6. Incubate in an aerobic incubator at 37°C for 18-24 hours.
7. Document on the DRUM eLIMS / teleform system
8. At the end of 18-24 hours incubation, take a 1.8ml aliquot of the culture media and place it in a cryovial for storage at -80°C. Generate freezer-safe LIMS barcode and apply to the tube and write the LIMS number on the tube also. Record position on stool box plan on DRUM shared drive (recording patient ID) and store at -80°C.
9. Keep the remaining culture in the fridge if not proceeding to culture within <2hrs, for future processing.
10. Otherwise, proceed to ESBL culture (SOP4).

5. Health and Safety

Please refer to risk assessment tools and local health and safety guidelines